

D4.6 Validation and Evaluation initial Report

Project ref. no.	Horizon 2020-SC5-2019-2 GA No. 869565
Project title	Vineyard Innovative Tool based on the InteGration of Earth Observation Services and in-field Sensors
Duration of the project	September 2020 - February 2024 (42 months)
WP/Task:	WP4
Document due Date:	April 30 th , 2023
Actual date of delivery	May 11 th , 2023
Leader of this deliverable	LINKS Foundation
Dissemination level	PUBLIC
Document status	Submitted

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 869565. This website reflects only the author's view and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Deliverable Information sheet

Version	Date	Author	Document history/approvals
0.1	15/04/2023	LINKS: Federico Oldani, Tommaso Monopoli, Giacomo Blanco, Dario Salza EURECAT: Marta Otero, Raimon Fabregat, Alex Pujol BSC: Núria Pérez-Zanón ELEAF: Jessica Snoek	Draft ready for internal review
0.2	21/04/2023	EURECAT: Marta Otero ELEAF: Jessica Snoek BSC: Andria Nicodemou	Review provided
0.3	26/04/2023	LINKS: Federico Oldani, Tommaso Monopoli, Giacomo Blanco, Dario Salza	Changes implemented
0.4	27/04/2023	UNINA: Boris Basile	Review provided
1	29/04/2023	Federico Oldani, Rosa Maria Araujo Rivero	Final review

Executive summary

The document outlines the validation process for the Intelligent Services developed as part of the VitiGEOSS project. This project aims to provide the winemaking community with cutting-edge tools to improve their sustainability practices and optimize their production processes.

In the second vegetative season (2022), the Intelligent Services are thoroughly validated using data collected from three demo sites. The performances of the VitiGEOSS services are monitored and evaluated using various metrics. This includes the ability of the tool to forecast vine phenology, monitor key crop indicators, provide climate prediction, predict the occurrence of vine diseases, deliver precise disease treatment recipes, optimize the use of resources and tasks, and evaluate sustainable indicators.

Data collected during this second season are used to calculate intermediate performance and propose improvements to be implemented in the third year. The final performance of the intelligent services will be determined using data from the third vegetative season (D4.7).

Overall, this document provides an overview of the validation process for the Intelligent Services developed as part of the VitiGEOSS project. These tools aim to help the winemaking community to improve their current strategies and move towards more sustainable practices as well as help them make decisions on a week to week basis throughout the growing season.

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List of abbreviations

DM	<i>Downy mildew</i>
DNN	<i>Deep Neural Network</i>
DT	<i>Decision Trees</i>
EC	<i>European Commission</i>
EO	<i>Earth Observation</i>
EU	<i>European Union</i>
GB	<i>Gradient Boosting</i>
KNN	<i>K-Nearest Neighbours</i>
LR	<i>Logistic Regression</i>
NB	<i>Naïve Bayes</i>
PM	<i>Powdery mildew</i>
RF	<i>Random Forest</i>
SVM	<i>Support Vector Machines</i>
WP	<i>Work Package</i>
KPI	<i>Key Performance Indicator</i>

Introduction

The objective of the VitiGEOSS project is to create a cohesive range of services that can provide valuable information to winemakers regarding various aspects of vineyard management, such as weather and climate forecasting, disease and phenology monitoring/forecasting, crop management, and sustainability. This will be accomplished through the integration of cutting-edge technology systems like satellite imagery, in-field sensors, and aerial images, which will facilitate the provision of Intelligent Services (IS), offering vital information on vineyard management aspects. The VitiGEOSS decision support system shall play a crucial role in enhancing the vineyard management process by providing forecasts, provisional models, and advanced visualization of the vineyard.

The weather and climate forecast service is a key element in informing users and providing predictions of atmospheric variables to other services in the platform. The deterministic weather forecast provides three hourly values for the next three days. The probabilistic sub-seasonal and seasonal climate forecasts anticipate probabilities of atmospheric variables for the next weeks and months. A description of the service and a review of the delivered products during the harvest season are included in section 1.

The monitoring and prediction of plant phenological cycles in response to weather conditions is an important tool providing useful information to improve, for instance, the timing of key agronomical practices like fertilization, pesticide application, irrigation, and harvesting schedules. In VitiGEOSS, we implement different models that provide novel approach solutions to phenology. The monitored phenology phases are bud break, blooming, fruit set, veraison, berry maturity (i.e., the maturation level desired for harvest), and leaf fall. The models use different data sources such as satellite imagery, weather stations, and climate predictions.

To provide a monitoring system able to consider the spatial variability of the management unit, images collected by drones will be used to determine and highlight zones of the vineyards characterized by lower vigor and water stress.

The key crop indicator service aims to monitor the crop status on a weekly basis during the growth season to assess the vegetation health status, crop productivity, crop water use, and crop nitrogen content. In addition, this service provides the user with an insight into the crop water demand for the upcoming week and a yield estimate for the upcoming season.

The disease monitoring and forecast models aim to anticipate vine diseases and treatment recommendations. These statistical and artificial intelligence (AI) models have been calibrated over the course of a vegetative season using real-time data provided by weather stations (temperature, precipitation, ambient humidity, wind speed, solar irradiation) together with phenological monitoring data and disease quantification in terms of percentage of incidence and severity measured in the six control subplots.

The business and sustainability management service aims to optimize the use of resources by the farmers by supporting them in taking decisions that can help define a more sustainable vineyard management strategy. The goal of this service is to help the technicians responsible for these tasks to take more informed decisions and provide an optimal schedule for organizing tasks, resources, and personnel available based on the scenario that the user provides.

The present deliverable addresses the evaluation of these services upon the second vegetative season (year 2022). A more extensive description of the services is available in D2.2 and D2.3.

Pilot plots used for data collection are located at the three demo sites, as follows:

- Portugal (Symington): Quinta do Ataíde and Quinta do Bomfim.
- Spain (Torres): Aranyó and Sant Martí Sarroca.
- Italy (Mastroberardino): Mirabella Eclano, Montefusco, Montemarano, Pietradefusi, and Santa Paolina.

More information about the pilot plots and the data collected in 2022 and used in the validation presented in this document, is available in D4.2.

1. Weather and climate forecasting services

Weather and climate conditions affect the development of the grapevines, and therefore, anticipating the atmospheric conditions will facilitate the management of the vineyards. Three types of data available in the VitiGEOSS platform cover three timescales: short-term, sub-seasonal, and seasonal. The short-term type is known as the weather forecast that provides information on the conditions in the following days, while sub-seasonal and seasonal are known as climate forecasts and give an indication of large-scale circulation patterns for the next weeks (sub-seasonal) and the next months (seasonal).

Complex dynamical models are run on high-performance computers to obtain weather and climate forecasts. Different climatic elements exert influence on the state of the surface conditions depending on the forecast horizon considered. In the case of short-term forecasts, the characterization of the initial state from which the atmosphere evolves is crucial. As the integration evolves, approximately after 10 days, the influence of the initial atmospheric conditions decays, and other climatic components become more relevant to forecast the evolution of the whole system, like the state of the land, ocean, ice, or other large-scale phenomena. For these time horizons, the type of forecast information that can be delivered differs from the short-term forecast. Instead of giving the exact expected value for a given instant, an average over a week or a month is provided, and the information is presented as deviations from normal conditions. Furthermore, the dynamical models are executed several times to estimate the uncertainties of the model outputs creating an ensemble of simulations. Therefore, the information from climate forecasts becomes probabilistic. In the VitiGEOSS climate forecast service, the model outputs for a set of variables are post-processed to provide the probabilities in three categories (Figure 1): below-normal, normal, or above-normal conditions.

Figure 1. Design of the climate forecast visualisation created during the project mock-ups. An idealised sub-seasonal forecast initialised on the 13th of May 2021 shows the air temperature forecast for the next four weeks.

Currently, mean, maximum and minimum air temperature at 2 m, accumulated precipitation, and solar radiation are the variables provided in the climate forecast services because these were the most relevant atmospheric surface variables detected during the co-development process with the vineyard managers. These variables are post-processed through an operational workflow which, among others, applies two crucial steps: bias adjustment to reduce systematic model errors, and downscaling to increase the spatial resolution of the forecast outputs. This

latest step allows us to provide tailored information on the locations of the vineyard plots of the users. As shown in Figure 1, in the case of the sub-seasonal forecast, the terciles probabilities are provided in the form of bars for each week. The light blue bar indicates the likelihood of the variable being below normal conditions, the grey bar is the probability of being within normal conditions, and the red bar is the probability of being above normal. The probabilities of the extremes, i.e. the probability of (not) exceeding the percentile (10) 90 are shown only in case they are greater than 40% in dark (blue) red bars.

A similar product is provided for the seasonal climate forecasts but, in that case, for the next three months. The color scale for the visualization of the forecasts of precipitation is different and was defined during the co-development process with the users involved in the project.

The assessment of the climate forecast products is done by calculating statistical metrics that compare past observations and retrospective forecasts (also known as hindcasts). These metrics are tailored to the product provided, in this case, the tercile categories. The results are shared along with the operational product. This aims to inform the users when the forecast provided for a specific place, initialization date, and forecast time has proven to be more accurate than using climatology. In case the metric is not positive, the bars in the plot are blurred, as shown in the second forecast week of Figure 1. In this case, the users can make the decisions in a business-as-usual way. Specifications of the datasets used post-processing methodologies and forecast verification were described in deliverables D2.2 and D2.3.

The probabilistic nature of climate forecasts is a limitation when assessing the products provided in 2022, first, because of the vast number of products delivered (i.e. probabilities for each location, initialization date, forecast month, and variable). Secondly, because they can fail to detect the most probable tercile category but there was a chance for the other categories to happen. Also, the positive statistical metrics enclosed with the products communicate the benefits of adopting the climate forecast in long-term usage, despite of fail in a specific forecast (Terrado et al., 2019). Therefore, we consider that this report could help illustrate how climate forecasts should be used by readers and the VitiGEOSS platform users. To this aim, we next analyze a case study focusing on the late summer and early autumn when the harvest take place. We think this topic can be relevant for the readers because it was a hot topic during the VitiGEOSS stakeholders' event in Italy in November 2022 (<https://vitigeoss.eu/local-stakeholder-event-italian/>).

1.1 Case study: climate forecast review from late summer to early autumn

The climate is essential in determining the harvest time (Mira de Orduña, 2010; Berbegal et al., 2019). Global warming is causing a shift forward in harvesting time in many wine regions. The optimal harvest date is usually between the end of August until early October. Hence, climate information in this season can be very beneficial for the wine industry. In particular, winemakers are quite interested in anticipating how the precipitation conditions will be during these months, since continuous precipitation in this period causes overcast skies, delaying the ripening of the grapes. In addition to that, an excess of rainfall during these months creates a surplus of water within the grapes, which, in turn, decreases the fruit sugar levels and sugar/acid balance that winemakers are looking for, thus having consequences on the wine flavor. Apart from that, grapes could bloat and even burst (causing spoilage), and, moreover, too much humidity favors mildew and fungus diseases. Several mechanisms can be activated to face such situations, but they all need accurate climate forecasts from August to October to optimize decision-making.

In the following subsections, the accumulated precipitation and mean temperature for the period July to October 2022 are explored using the ERA5-Land reanalysis (Muñoz-Sabater et al., 2021) for the Campania, Catalonia, and Douro regions where the climate services in VitiGEOSS are provided.

1.1.1 Campania region

During the VitiGEOSS local [stakeholders' event in Italy](#) in November 2022, viticulturists mentioned the impact of temperatures on the acidity of the grapes. The first step is to explore the observed mean temperature and accumulated precipitation from July to October 2022 (Figure 2). In this case, the percentiles and mean of the temperatures and precipitation have been computed for the period 1993-2022 to determine the 'normal' conditions expected.

As mentioned during the local stakeholder event, the temperatures in the Campania region were higher than normal in July and August 2022. This is shown in Figure 2 (left), where temperatures are shown to be higher than the 66th percentile for 6 out of 7 weeks from July to mid-August. Then, the temperatures dropped to normal conditions for two weeks. At the same time, precipitation events in the week starting on the 29th of August were quite abundant in the region, in the range of the 90th percentile for that week of the year (Figure 2, right).

Figure 2 2022 daily and weekly evolution of ERA5-Land temperature (left) and accumulated precipitation (right) in the Campania region showing the climatological mean and percentiles (blue shadows and lines) computed for the period 1993-2022.

Given the short length of the rainfall events, we first explored the sub-seasonal climate forecasts provided for the specific weeks. Forecasts for the week starting on the 29th of August issued 4, 3, 2, and 1 week in advance are shown in Figure 3. In the northwest area, the above-normal accumulated precipitation is forecasted for all initialization dates. In the southeast area, the signal changed from above-normal to below-normal conditions in later initialization dates.

Figure 3 NCEP-CFSv2 weekly accumulated precipitation probabilistic forecast of most likely tercile category for the week starting the 29th of August 2022 forecasted 4 (top-left), 3 (top-right), 2 (bottom-left) and 1 week in advance (bottom-right). Where the skill score is below zero, no points are displayed.

For the week starting on the 26th of September 2022, the forecasts initialized 4, 3, 2, and 1 week in advance have been considered, shown in Figure 4. The north-western region presented positive skill for all initialization dates, while the southeast part only showed positive skill for the forecast initialized one week in advance when above-normal accumulated precipitation was the most probable outcome for the whole region.

Figure 4 NCEP-CFSv2 weekly accumulated precipitation probabilistic forecast of the most likely tercile category for the week starting on the 26th of September 2022 forecasted 4 (top-left), 3 (top-right), 2 (bottom-left), and 1 week in advance (bottom-right). Where the skill score is below zero, no points are displayed.

On the other hand, the seasonal climate forecasts targeted for September did not show better skill than the climatology when anticipating the accumulated precipitation 1, 2, or 3 months in advance. This result is due to the limitations of the current climate prediction systems at the specific time of the year investigated, as the large circulation patterns that can bring predictability to the system tend to be less strong than in other months/seasons (Fllis, 2022). Furthermore, the representation of the convective processes associated with the occurrence of precipitation events needs to be improved for the future generation of climate prediction systems. In this situation, users are encouraged to base their decisions on past climate observations either by conducting a business-as-usual or considering a payoff function for different climate conditions (Vigo et al., 2018; Vigo et al., under-review). In any case, it is not recommended to consider a climate forecast based on persistence (as it was suggested in the

stakeholders' session) because this approach does not consider the annual cycle of the temperature and precipitation conditions.

Figure 5. ECMWF SEAS5 monthly accumulated precipitation probabilistic forecast of the most likely tercile category for September 2022 forecasted 3 (top-left), 2 (top-right), and 1 month in advance (bottom-left). Where the skill score is below zero, no points are displayed.

1.1.2 Douro region

In general, the temperatures were above normal during July and August 2022 in the Douro region (Figure 6.). From the last week of August to the first two weeks of September, the temperatures decreased and were within normal conditions for that time of the year, oscillating between the terciles limits. Then, until the end of October, the temperatures increased again, except for the week starting the 26th of September. The precipitation was below normal until the week starting on the 12th of September. In the last two weeks of October, the accumulated precipitation in the region increased again.

Figure 6. The daily and weekly evolution of ERA5-Land temperature (left) and accumulated precipitation (right) in the Douro region in 2022, showing the climatological mean and percentiles (blue shadows and lines) computed for the period 1993-2022.

Similar to the Campania region in Italy, the sub-seasonal climate forecast in the Douro region anticipated one week in advance (forecast issued on the 8th of September) the above-normal accumulated precipitation seen during the week starting on the 12th of September (Figure 7).

Figure 7. NCEP-CFSv2 weekly accumulated precipitation probabilistic forecast of the most likely tercile category for the week starting the 12th of September 2022 forecasted 4 (top-left), 3 (top-right), 2 (bottom-left), and 1 week in advance (bottom-right). Where the skill score is below zero, no points are displayed.

The seasonal climate forecasts for the region anticipated dry and normal conditions for accumulated precipitation 3 months in advance, normal conditions 2 months in advance, and a combination of the three categories 1 month in advance (Figure 8.). This region presents larger areas with positive skill scores, but the probabilities ranged from 34-49% in most of the locations. The difficulties of the seasonal forecasts to correctly reproduce the precipitation patterns in this region are probably related to the short length of the precipitation events.

Figure 8. ECMWF SEAS5 monthly accumulated precipitation probabilistic forecast of the most likely tercile category for September 2022 forecasted 3 (top-left), 2 (top-right), and 1 month in advance (bottom-left). Where the skill score is below zero, no points are displayed

1.1.3 Catalonia region

The weekly mean temperatures from July to October 2022 in the Catalonia region were extremely high for 9 out of 17 weeks, and only 3 weeks were in the normal or below-normal category (Figure 9.). The evolution of the area-averaged accumulated precipitation shows a

heavy rainfall event at the beginning of July and several events from the last week of July until the middle of October. In the last week examined, there were no precipitation events for the reanalysis dataset to capture in the region.

Figure 9. The daily and weekly evolution of ERA5-Land temperature (left) and accumulated precipitation (right) in the Catalonia region in 2022, showing the climatological mean and percentiles (blue shadows and lines) computed for the period 1993-2022.

In this case, seasonal climate forecasts anticipating the September conditions in the Catalonia region presented positive skill scores in large areas when initialized 1, 2, and 3 months in advance (Figure 10.). The signal between normal to above normal accumulated precipitation during September was consistent with the monthly observed accumulated precipitation.

Figure 10. ECMWF SEAS5 monthly accumulated precipitation probabilistic forecast of the most likely tercile category for September 2022 forecasted 3 (top-left), 2 (top-right), and 1 month in advance (bottom-left). Where the skill score is below zero, no points are displayed

In this case, the sub-seasonal climate forecast could be used to anticipate a dry week. During the week of the 24th of October, there were no precipitation events for the reanalysis dataset to capture in the Catalonia region. The extension of the area in which the sub-seasonal climate forecast was able to perform better than the climatology is larger for 1 and 4 weeks in advance than for 2 and 3 weeks in advance (Figure 11.). The sub-seasonal forecasts issued 1 and 2 weeks in advance agreed on the below normal accumulated precipitation in the target week.

Figure 11. NCEP-CFSv2 weekly accumulated precipitation probabilistic forecast of the most likely tercile category for the week starting the 24th of October 2022 forecasted 4 (top-left), 3 (top-right), 2 (bottom-left), and 1 week in advance (bottom-right). Where the skill score is below zero, no points are displayed.

1.2 Annual evolution of the sub-seasonal climate skill

Given the novelty of including sub-seasonal climate forecasts in the climate services for sustainability vineyard management, the detection of the windows of opportunity at sub-seasonal timescales has been considered. This analysis has been carried out by exploring the periods when the skill score was higher than 0. In that case, the locations where vineyard plots are located have been selected, and the skill scores of each site have been mapped as a function of the initialization date and the forecasted week. An example has been chosen given the number of combinations and the generally good performance of the sub-seasonal forecast for the products provided. As expected, the skill scores decrease when the forecast week increases, since the forecast loses the predictability brought by the initial conditions (Figure 12). The skill of the temperature in the selected locations shows positive values during most of the year, except for a few weeks in early summer. Even with this lack of positive skill in early summer, the sub-seasonal climate forecast can be handy because it performs well for spring and autumn, which are very relevant seasons for managing vineyards.

Figure 12. Mean air temperature at 2m skill scores (RPSS; in percentage) by forecast week for all initialization dates in 2022 and locations in Campania (top), Douro (middle), and Catalonia (bottom).

1.3 Summary

Users are informed about the skill of seasonal and sub-seasonal climate forecasts. For each place, variable, initialization and forecast time, a statistical value is calculated to assess if, during the past, the forecast product provided has performed better than the climatological values. Therefore, every time the forecast product is updated (i.e. every month in the case of the seasonal climate forecasts and weekly in the case of the sub-seasonal climate forecasts), the users can see not only the actual forecast but also their added value against traditional usage of the climatological values. In case the climate forecast products are skilful, the added value of including them in their decision-making chain will be shown in the long term.

The local stakeholder event held in Italy in November 2022 (<https://vitigeoss.eu/local-stakeholder-event-italian/>) was very relevant from the climate research perspective. First, it helped us to understand how climatic conditions affect harvest time. The observed related variables have been explored to detect the crucial dates. Using those dates, the sub-seasonal and seasonal climate forecast has been explored to report the anticipated information. Rather than focusing on the detection of the most probable tercile category for a specific year, we aim to emphasize the relevance of the skill scores provided operationally because of their temporal and spatial variability. For instance, temperatures and solar radiation have higher and more frequent positive skill scores than precipitation.

During the local stakeholder session, some users pointed out that they might be using forecasts based on persistence rather than climatology. We recommend using climatology and trying to find channels to work with users on adding climatology and climate forecast as part of the information in their decision-making chain.

Finally, new efforts are underway to improve the climate forecasts by the climate research community. For example, the Copernicus climate change service evolution project (CERISE; <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101082139>), funded by the European Commission's Horizon Europe Framework Programme, investigates innovative balanced land-atmosphere initialisation methodologies for seasonal climate forecasts with a focus on the consistency between hindcasts and real-time land surface initial conditions.

2. Phenology services

This section presents the validation of the phenological models. They are divided into detection models, aimed at monitoring the phenological status of the crop, and forecast models, aimed at providing a prediction of the next phenological phases up to four weeks ahead. The models are based on the historical data of the varieties Syrah, Touriga Nacional, Touriga Franca, Aglianico and Greco (this last cultivar only for the mechanistic model that requires less historical data for the calibration process).

2.1 Phenology detection models

2.1.1 Deep Weather Observation model

The Deep Weather model first described in section 2.2.2.1 of D2.2 and with the updates reported in section 2.2.1.1 of D2.3 is hereby evaluated using 2022 data. The model has been trained on all data available from 2017 to 2021 included. Gaps in the measurements due to weather station malfunction (very common for Tenuta Radici, while extremely rare for all the other pilot plots) have been filled by interpolation when missing a single sample or by unbiasing of neighbouring weather stations with publicly available data when the gaps are longer. The model shows the same performance level as that reported in the previous deliverable (D2.3), with a Mean Absolute Error (MAE) of 4.3 days. A notable outlier in the otherwise good results is, however, the 21 days of error in predicting the veraison phase for the Touriga Franca variety in the Bomfim location. This is also due to the fact that the true observed date is itself an outlier, as confirmed by the end user, as veraison has occurred in the considered parcel much later than usual and than in the other cultivars or parcels.

Absolute Error (Days)						
Cultivar / Phase	Bud Break	Blooming	FruitSet	Veraison	Ripening	Average
Aranyo Syrah	5	1	1	2	3	2.4
Ataide Touriga Franca	1	1	8	5	5	4
Ataide Touriga Nacional	0	1	5	8	1	3
Bomfim Touriga Franca	8	4	3	21	8	8.8
Bomfim Touriga Nacional	1	1	8	1	11	4.4
Tenuta Radici Aglianico	5	3	6	1	1	3.2
Average	3.33	1.83	5.17	6.33	4.83	4.3

Table 1 - Evaluation of Deep Weather model in 2022.

As in the deliverables D2.3 and D2.4, the performance is compared to the one produced by a GDD (Growing Degree Days) model calibrated using the same data, showing that the Deep Weather Observation model has a lower absolute error on average (4.3 against 5.9).

Absolute Error (Days)						
Cultivar / Phase	Bud Break	Blooming	FruitSet	Veraison	Ripening	Average
Aranyo Syrah	7	2	4	5	8	5.2
Ataide Touriga Franca	11	0	/	1	14	6.5
Ataide Touriga Nacional	5	2	/	0	12	4.75

Bomfim Touriga Franca	6	3	3	25	18	11
Bomfim Touriga Nacional	2	1	1	5	0	1.8
Tenuta Radici Aglianico	7	0	10	5	7	5.8
Average	6.33	1.33	4.50	6.83	9.83	5.9

Table 2 - Evaluation of GDD on weather station data in 2022.

2.1.2 Deep EO3 model

In this section, we evaluate the Deep Earth Observation (Deep EO3) model described in Section 2.2.1.2 of Deliverable 2.3 on the vegetative season of 2022. The model has been trained on all data collected between 2017 and 2021 in pilot vineyards. We did not use any validation data. We tried to reduce the error in the training data as much as possible. The results of the evaluation of this model are presented in Table 3. The magnitude of the mean absolute error is about one week for most of the phenological phases and pilot vineyards, as shown by the overall average error of 8.03 days.

Cultivar	MAE (Days)					
	Bud break	Flowering	Fruit-set	Veraison	Ripening	Average
Aranyo Syrah	7	4	11	6	23	10.20
Ataide Touriga Franca	0	4	8	10	3	5.00
Ataide Touriga Nacional	8	7	4	25	5	9.80
Bomfim Touriga Franca	12	3	3	11	4	6.60
Bomfim Touriga Nacional	11	2	16	4	25	11.60
Tenuta Radici Aglianico	9	1	5	2	8	5.00
Average	7.83	3.50	7.83	9.67	11.33	8.03

Table 3 - Evaluation result of Deep EO3 model in 2022.

As in Deliverable 2.3, the Deep EO3 model performances have been compared with the GDD baseline model in 2022. The GDD thresholds have been computed considering data between 2017 and 2021 and have been used to predict the occurrence of phenological phases for pilot vineyards in 2022, reporting the results in Table 4. Unlike the Deep EO3 model, GDD shows most of the time an absolute error greater than a week, remarked by the overall error of 16.86 days. These results, in addition to the previous CV results reported in D2.3, indicate that the Deep EO3 model has a better performance in phenology detection compared to the GDD model.

Cultivar	MAE (Days)					
	Bud break	Flowering	Fruit set	Veraison	Ripening	Average
Aranyo Syrah	41	1	1	8	2	10.6
Ataide Touriga Franca	20	9	ND	16	47	23
Ataide Touriga Nacional	14	12	ND	13	41	20

Bomfim Touriga Franca	3	11	14	16	44	17.60
Bomfim Touriga Nacional	19	8	11	15	18	14.20
Tenuta Radici Aglianico	10	7	22	29	21	17.80
Average	17.83	8.00	12.00	16.17	28.83	16.89

Table 4 - Evaluation results of GDD model with satellite data in 2022

2.2 Phenology forecast models

2.2.1 Deep Weather Forecast model

Together with the observation use case discussed in Section 2.1.1, the Deep Weather Forecast model was also evaluated in the forecast paradigm introduced in section 2.2.1.6 of D2.3. Here, the model takes as an input the measurements of the weather stations up to a certain base date, and the corrected weather forecast for the following days. The base date is selected as 7 and 14 days before each phenological event, measuring thus the error of forecasting a phenological stage one and two weeks before its occurrence. Where “0” forecasted days is shown, it corresponds to the observation paradigm, with only real measured data. The model evaluated here is the same as the one in the Deep Weather Observation model (Section 2.1.1), and is trained on 2017-2021 historical data.

Variety	Forecasted days	Bud Break	Flowering	Fruit-set	Veraison	Ripening	Average error
Aranyo Syrah	0	5	1	1	2	3	2.4
	7	1	2	1	2	3	1.8
	14	1	4	0	1	3	1.8
Ataide Touriga Franca	0	1	1	8	5	5	4.0
	7	0	3	10	7	5	5.0
	14	3	5	10	7	5	6.0
Ataide Touriga Nacional	0	0	1	5	8	1	3.0
	7	1	0	6	9	1	3.4
	14	1	2	8	16	2	5.8
Bomfim Touriga Franca	0	8	4	3	21	8	8.8
	7	8	3	4	21	8	8.8
	14	7	0	6	21	8	8.4
Bomfim Touriga Nacional	0	1	1	8	1	11	4.4
	7	0	5	10	0	11	5.2
	14	0	6	12	2	16	7.2
Mirabella Eclano Aglianico	0	5	3	6	1	1	3.2
	7	3	6	6	1	1	3.4
	14	3	7	6	1	1	3.6

Table 5-Absolute errors (in days) of Deep Weather model according to number of forecasted days in 2022

Forecasted days	Average error
0	4.3
7	4.6
14	5.5

Table 6-Average number of days of errors, across all varieties, of Deep Weather model depending on number of forecasted days

The performances obtained with this paradigm are also compared with those obtained with a GDD approach, showing again that the Deep Weather model gives better results than the GDD irrespective of the number of days of forecasted measures.

Variety	Forecasted days	Bud Break	Flowering	Fruit-set	Veraison	Ripening	Average error
Aranyo Syrah	0	7	2	4	5	8	5.2
	7	7	2	4	4	8	5
	14	6	6	2	2	7	4.6
Ataide Touriga Franca	0	11	0	/	1	14	6.5
	7	8	3	/	1	14	6.5
	14	8	7	/	3	14	8
Ataide Touriga Nacional	0	5	2	/	0	12	4.75
	7	1	1	/	2	12	4
	14	2	2	/	5	12	5.25
Bomfim Touriga Franca	0	6	3	3	25	18	11
	7	6	1	2	25	18	10.4
	14	3	3	2	25	18	10.2
Bomfim Touriga Nacional	0	2	1	1	5	0	1.8
	7	5	6	4	5	2	4.4
	14	4	7	8	2	4	5
Mirabella Eclano Aglianico	0	7	0	10	5	7	5.8
	7	2	2	10	6	7	5.4
	14	3	5	10	6	8	6.4

Table 7 - Absolute errors (in days) of GDD model according to number of forecasted days in 2022

Forecasted days	Average error
0	5.9
7	6.0
14	6.6

Table 8-Average number of days of errors, across all varieties, of GDD model depending on number of forecasted days

2.2.2 Mechanistic model

As for the other models, the Mechanistic model was also evaluated in the forecast paradigm introduced in 2.2.1.6 of D2.3. The model uses measurements of the weather stations up to a certain base date as defined below, and the corrected weather forecasts for the following days. The base dates are 7 and 14 days before each observed phenological event, thus providing an estimate of the error of forecasting a phenological stage one and two weeks before its occurrence. The 0 forecasted days correspond to simulation results using only weather station measured data. Table 9 reports the mean absolute error between observations and simulations of all the plots for each calibrated variety according to the number of forecasting days (0, 7 and 14). Table 10 shows the average error among all varieties for each forecasting time.

The presented results for the year 2022 show an increase in the average error as the forecast time increases. Compared to the simulations performed with weather station data (0 days of forecast), the error increases by approximately 1.5 days per week of forecast, thus most of the source of error in the predictions comes from the base calibration of each variety's parameters. These results should further improve after the next growing season.

Variety	Forecasted days	Bud Break	Flowering	Fruit-set	Veraison	Ripening	Average error
Aglianico	0	6.7	4.3	6.3	4.0	9.3	6.1
	7	8.2	5.3	6.8	5.3	10.5	7.2
	14	10.4	6.5	8.2	8.4	13.7	9.4
Greco	0	9.8	4.5	5.0	8.0	6.5	6.8
	7	12.4	5.7	5.5	7.3	8.4	7.9
	14	15.8	5.3	6.6	11.3	12.5	10.3
Syrah	0	9.7	4.8	5.7	9.2	8.3	7.5
	7	9.1	4.7	7.5	10.1	12.2	8.7
	14	11.0	5.4	8.3	12.7	12.5	10.0
Touriga Franca	0	10.8	4.0	5.3	11.7	9.8	8.3
	7	12.3	5.8	6.8	13.9	14.3	10.6
	14	12.6	6.2	7.6	15.2	15.6	11.4
Touriga Nacional	0	12.2	5.8	6.3	10.3	11.6	9.2
	7	13.6	7.1	6.9	12.4	13.1	10.6
	14	14.5	7.9	8.1	14.1	14.9	11.9

Table 9-Mean absolute errors (in days) of the Mechanistic model according to number of forecasted days in 2022

Forecasted days	Average error
0	7.6
7	9.0
14	10.6

Table 10-Average number of days of error, across all varieties, of the Mechanistic model depending on the number of forecasted days

2.3 Deep drone service

The service provides vineyard managers with a tool for monitoring the health of their crops, identifying potential issues before they become widespread, and making data-driven decisions about how to manage their vineyards. The service is described in more detail in deliverables D2.2 and D2.3.

The main advantage of using images taken by Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) rather than satellite images is their resolution. While the satellite images have a resolution of 10 m per pixel, the drone images have a minimum resolution of 20 cm per pixel. This requirement allows to identify the vineyard rows and filter out the grass that grows between the rows. Therefore, the vegetative analysis on drone images is more accurate rather than satellite images. However, a disadvantage is the high cost of drone flights, which allows just a few flights during the vegetative season. The use of both sources is useful for continuous and accurate monitoring of the vineyard.

The analysis performed over the drone imagery is:

- **Segmentation:** a deep learning model segments the vineyard rows from RGB drone images
- **Vineyard density map:** A heatmap of the areas covered by vineyard row pixels is produced. The resulting image highlights areas where the grapevines are absent and where the grapevine growth is slower than in other areas in the same vineyard. The vineyard density index is discussed in depth in section 2.3.1.
- **Rows vNDVI:** a vegetation index computed on vineyard rows is produced. It helps in detecting more stressed areas.
- **Interrows vNDVI:** a vegetation index computed on the interrow areas is produced. The result highlights the areas covered by grass, that might compete for resources such as water, nutrients, and sunlight. This competition can reduce grapevine performances.

The validation process reported in this section focuses on the aforementioned analysis steps. The drone flights have been planned and performed by each end-user during the vegetative season. In 2022, the flights performed were the following:

Company	Field coverage	Flight dates
Mastroberardino	MONTE ST 1 MONTE ST 2 MONTE ST 3	2022-06-13
		2022-06-28
		2022-07-29
		2022-09-14
		2022-10-28
Torres	Agrolab PM1 Agrolab PM2 Agrolab PM3	2022-05-20
		2022-06-10
		2022-07-01
		2022-07-29

		2022-08-18 2022-08-31
Symington	ATD 94 ATD 102	2022-07-10 2022-07-24 2022-08-03 2022-08-15 2022-08-29 2022-09-10

2.3.1 Vineyard density index

The vineyard density index is a vegetation index that is computed on a vineyard segmentation mask. It provides a quantitative measure of the density of the rows and the thickness of the grapevines in a small square region centred at each pixel. Figure 13 visually explains how the vineyard density index is computed.

Figure 13 - Vineyard density computation

Vineyard density at pixel (i, j) is given by the formula:

$$d_L(i, j) = \frac{\# \text{ vine pixels in } W_{i,j}^{(L)}}{\# \text{ pixels in } W_{i,j}^{(L)}}$$

where $W_{i,j}^{(L)}$ is the square window centred in (i, j) and of side L (in pixels). The window slides across the whole image to compute the vineyard density at each point.

The side L of the sliding window can be set according to the level of detail desired: higher values of L mean that more neighbouring pixels are taken into account, giving a more “aggregated”, coarser appearance to the heatmap, whereas lower values of L capture finer, lower-level details. This behaviour is visualized in Figure 14.

Figure 14 - Effects of the choice of L on the vineyard density heatmap

Note that the choice of L should take into account the resolution of the drone image: at a higher resolution, also L should be chosen larger, since inter-row pixel distance increases.

The Vineyard Density Index (VDI) can be compared with the Leaf Area Index (LAI), with the main difference being that the VDI is computed solely on the vineyard rows, while the LAI considers all the vegetative areas (grass, bushes, trees).

2.3.2 Analysis

As mentioned previously, the segmentation of the vineyard rows is the first step of the vineyard analysis pipeline. Since the UAV images collected have not been labelled, it is not possible to derive quantitative measures about the quality of the output segmentation masks. However, we can still perform a qualitative evaluation by visually inspecting segmentation masks and their corresponding UAV image. Hereafter, some examples are reported.

Figure 15 - Example of row segmentation (Mastroberardino, MONTE ST 2, 13/06/2022)

Figure 16 - Example of row segmentation (Mastroberardino, MONTE ST 2, 29/07/2022)

Figure 17 - Example of row segmentation (Mastroberardino, MONTE ST 2, 28/10/2022)

Figure 18 - Example of row segmentation (Symington, ATD 94, 24/07/2022)

Figure 19 - Example of row segmentation (Torres, Agrolab PM1, 29/07/2022)

Figure 20 - Example of row segmentation (Torres, Agrolab PM1, 31/08/2022)

Figure 21 - Example of row segmentation (Torres, Agrolab PM3, 29/07/2022)

The deep learning segmentation model achieves overall good results. It is capable of locating vineyard rows in UAV images at different resolutions (compare for instance Figure 15/Figure 18/Figure 19), different light exposures (Figure 15/Figure 16) and different vine thickness/growth (Figure 19/Figure 20). Moreover, it exhibits good robustness against green objects which are not vines: grass and small plants growing between rows (Figure 15/Figure 15 - Example of row segmentation (Mastroberardino, MONTE ST 2, 13/06/2022), Figure 16, Figure 19, Figure 20) and trees (Figure 15/Figure 15 - Example of row segmentation (Mastroberardino, MONTE ST 2, 13/06/2022), Figure 16, Figure 17). On the other hand, at the current version, the model has some limitations: it is not sufficiently robust against shadows projected by tall objects such as trees (Figure 16), it cannot accurately recognize brown-coloured (dry) vines (Figure 17) and may miss moderately large portions of vineyard rows at times (Figure 21). These issues will be addressed in future versions of the segmentation model.

The segmentation mask returned by the model can then be exploited for many different downstream analysis tasks, such as the ones mentioned earlier (computation of vineyard density

and vNDVI indexes). A single result of our analysis is reported hereafter, as an example. The complete results of the analysis are reported in annex 8.1, for each vineyard and each flight date.

Figure 22 - Mastroberardino, MONTE ST 1 (top) and MONTE ST 2 (bottom), 13-06-2022

Figure 23 Sentinel-2 Mastroberardino, MONTE ST 1 (top) and MONTE ST 2 (bottom), 16-06-2022

2.3.3 Temporal analysis

In this section, a time-series analysis is performed. The NDVI and LAI measured by Sentinel-2 are compared to the Visible Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (vNDVI) and the Vineyard Density Map (VDM) computed over the UAV images. One crucial factor to bear in mind is that the visible vNDVI is computed based on Red-Green-Blue (RGB) imagery, and each image is captured under differing light conditions, thereby making the vNDVI potentially unreliable. However, it is discernible that the vNDVI manifests a clear declining trend from May to October in the three pilot plots as expected in a vineyard, which attains the peak of the vegetative phase during late spring. In contrast, the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) derived from Sentinel-2 data often exhibits noise and does not accurately portray the NDVI behaviour in the vineyard.

The Leaf Area Index (LAI) measured by Sentinel-2 is an effective means of capturing the vegetation development of the vineyard. However, it is important to note that this data may also contain a degree of noise and may not always be entirely exploitable. Instead, the corresponding Vineyard Density Map (VDM) reflects the behaviour of the LAI and it appears more stable. This suggests that the VDM may serve as a useful tool for analysing and understanding the growth patterns and density of the vineyard. Further evaluation and analysis of both the vNDVI and VDM data sets could provide valuable insights and inform decision-making processes related to vineyard management and production.

Figure 24 (left) NDVI Sentinel-2 and vNDVI UAV images, (right) LAI Sentinel-2 and Vineyard Density Map (VDM) on UAV images. Torres vineyard

Figure 25 (left) NDVI Sentinel-2 and vNDVI UAV images, (right) LAI Sentinel-2 and Vineyard Density Map (VDM) on UAV images. Symington vineyards

Figure 26 (left) NDVI Sentinel-2 and vNDVI UAV images, (right) LAI Sentinel-2 and Vineyard Density Map (VDM) on UAV images. Mastroberardino vineyards

2.4 Deep Camera

In this section, we evaluate the results of the segmentation model described in Section 2.2.1.3 of Deliverable 2.3. The images collected in pilot vineyards have not been labelled, so it is not possible to derive quantitative measures of the quality of the developed model. We then perform a qualitative evaluation by manually inspecting an image for each installed camera, reporting the result in Figure 27.

Figure 27. Prediction of the segmentation model for an image for each installed camera. Segmented in red the grapes, in green the leaves.

Overall, good results are shown by the model in classifying pixels representing leaves (green blobs in prediction in Figure 27), covering most of the leaf area and at the same time distinguishing them from the grass with few exceptions. Despite the good results in segmenting leaf areas, the model still performs some errors, which may be due to the illumination conditions that are very different from the ones seen during training or for leaves that have already changed their colour in autumn. Regarding the classification of grapes pixels (red blobs in prediction in Figure 27), while the model shows high precision when the grapes are clearly visible, some difficulties arise when they are covered by leaves. It is still able to detect the presence of grapes in the image, but it is more likely to over-estimate their size, incorrectly classifying regions that contain leaves or background as grapes.

In the previous Deliverable D2.3, the possibility of using the presented segmentation model, together with some visual indexes, for vineyard lifecycle monitoring was discussed. In order to assess the feasibility of this action, the BRI (Blue Red Index) index evolution in each installed camera was compared with the phenological phases communicated by winegrowers, reporting the results in Figure 28.

Figure 28 Evolution of BRI index on detected grapes segment for each installed camera

In each plot, purple is used to indicate the evolution of the BRI index evaluated considering only a portion of the images classified as grapes by the segmentation model, as well as the extension of the grapes segment, shown in blue and expressed as a percentage over the extent of the whole image. Only images collected after the occurrence of fruit set have been considered, since there are no grapes to detect prior to this phase. In each plot, it is possible to identify a common trend with some general properties: despite local fluctuations, which might be due to the illumination condition and the quality of prediction on the single image, the index value constantly increases from fruit set until ripening, when the grapes are harvested by winegrowers and are not detected anymore by the model. Since index evolution could also provide insights into the phenological status of the vine, we have recorded the index value measured on the day each phase occurred, reporting the results in Table 9. Unfortunately, as data collection for only one year is available for each camera, this approach may suffer from low robustness and has yet to be tested, regardless, it is still worth validating its results in the 2023 vegetative season.

Vineyard	Variety	Camera	Fruit Set	Veraison	Ripening
Bomfim	Touriga Nacional	0700D52A	-0,088	-0,023	0,043
Aranyo	Syrah	0700D570	0,015	0,021	0,030
Aranyo	Syrah	0700D571	-0,028	-0,028	-0,046

Aranyo	Syrah	0700D572	-0,078	0,071	0,101
Tenuta Radici	Aglianico	0700D64C	-0,051	0,139	0,551
Ataide	Touriga Nacional	0700D79D	0,058	0,058	0,230
Montemarano	Aglianico	0700E7EC	-0,012	0,080	0,192
Tenuta Radici	Greco	0700E7EF	-0,303	-0,141	-0,072
Ataide	Touriga Francesa	0700E288	-0,187	0,063	0,212

Table 9 - Value of BRI index at the occurrence of each phase for pilot vineyards

In the previous Deliverable D2.3, we also introduced vegetation indices that could be calculated on leaf segments of camera images obtained by the segmentation model. This section presents a comparison of the temporal variation of the vNDVI index, derived from camera images, with NDVI obtained from Sentinel 2 satellite, and reports the result in Figure 29. In addition, for these plots, we have reported the total extent of leaf segments as a percentage over the whole image. Both vNDVI and NDVI indices are expected to exhibit similar temporal patterns, as they both measure the vegetation's greenness and health. However, the plots demonstrate that the vNDVI and NDVI indices differ significantly and are even divergent for most of the 9 cameras considered.

Figure 29 Comparison of vNDVI from cameras and NDVI from Sentinel 2 satellite for each installed camera

Several reasons could account for this disparity. The segmentation model may not be precise enough to differentiate leaves from grapes and the background, particularly under different illumination conditions. For some plots, it is possible to observe long periods with no data due to the absence of leaf segments in model predictions. As previously said, different illumination conditions may have impacted the performances of the segmentation model, as well as the status of the camera sensor which may have been dirty for some periods due to rain or soil. In addition, various factors, such as atmospheric conditions, may impact the accuracy of NDVI index. In fact, satellite data appears to be more problematic. While the vNDVI extracted from camera images appears to be more in line, despite some fluctuations, with the occurrence of phenological phases, the NDVI appears to decline for most cameras when the vegetative stage of the plant is at its peak and increasing when approaching, and even after, the leaf fall. The spatial resolution of satellite data may have affected the quality of data acquisition: since satellite data are obtained as the average value registered over a relatively large area, it may happen that these values are referred more to the ground, measuring the vegetative status of weeds, than to grape plants themselves.

3. Key crop indicators tracking services

The Key Crop Indicators are services aimed to monitor the crop status on a weekly basis during the growing season to assess the vegetation health status, crop productivity, crop water use, and crop nitrogen content. The key crop indicators exist of a series of datasets providing information on the vines with different time intervals. Among those indicators are crop parameters, yield estimation, and crop water demand. The crop parameters and crop water demand are delivered on a weekly basis and the yield estimation per season. The crop parameters calculated include actual biomass production, actual crop evapotranspiration, nitrogen content and Normalized Vegetation Index (NDVI).

This chapter will focus on the quality of the key crop parameters data looking back on the past season. All the Key crop indicators are fed through the API; Data parameters, Yield forecast information and Crop water demand. The evaluation of the quality of the key crop indicators is done by the team of eLEAF as well as by the end users. Sessions have been held between the eLEAF team and all end users separately to discuss anomalies and possible discrepancies in the data.

3.1 Key Crop indicators in the platform

The crop parameters are displayed in varies ways, when logging on to the VitiGEOSS platform a user will see a color-coded overview of their fields. In the image below you can find an example for the parameter Biomass production that is selected, see top left. We are looking at the fields of one farm in this case for week 14 2023, we can see that one field shows relatively higher values, two relatively lower and the rest of them coded yellow are within the -15% and +15% of average. This can help prioritize the users' actions. When clicking on a specific field the user can find more in-depth information on the values.

VitiGEOSS platform landing page with an overview of color-coded fields for the parameter biomass production.

When zooming in to one specific field the user finds this page shown below. It is possible to select only one of the parameters by clicking on it, the others will disappear out of the graph. It is also possible to select those you would like to compare and to zoom in to a certain period.

Overview of crop parameters for one field over the whole 2022 season.

Per field and per parameter the spatial information is shown in the platform as well, when selecting a field an enlarged version pops out for detail.

Spatial overview per parameter for the selected field, when clicking on one of the smaller maps an enlargement pops up.

3.2 Crop parameters

The crop parameters calculated include actual biomass production, actual crop evapotranspiration, nitrogen content and Normalized Vegetation Index (NDVI). This information is supported by the operational data production structure derived from the ETLook model (Pelgrum et al., 2012). In addition to the processing structure managed in ETLook, there are other parameters derived from the combination of spectral bands captured with the satellite sensor. This is the case for the nitrogen content in canopy and nitrogen content in upper leaf and Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI).

Before pushing the data onto the platform, the data is automatically checked on its values and manually checked on unexpected patterns. The team of eLEAF has automated the process of checking on outliers, the team will be notified if a parameter reaches a certain value that has been shown untrustworthy. This starts with the input data and ends with the final datasets shown on the platform.

After the 2022 season had ended the eLEAF team organized sessions with all end-users involved in the VitiGEOSS project to run through the seasons data. The focus was on weather events, noticeable stress that had been picked up by the farmers and correlation with ground truthing data. The correlation and events on site were picked up well in the dataset and by looking back on the past events the users will have a better understanding of what to focus on for 2023.

3.3 Yield estimation

Two machine learning algorithms (Random Forest and Gradient Boosting) were trained on historical grape yield data for prediction and forecasting of the grape yield. The performance of both models at 10-fold cross-validation was similar: coefficient of determination $R^2 = 0.58$ (+/-0.08), mean absolute error MAE = 9.46 (+/-0.08) q ha⁻¹, root-mean-square error RMSE = 12.30 (+/-1.14) q ha⁻¹, bias = -0.08 (+/-1.49) q ha⁻¹.

RMSE

The addition of weather data slightly improved the metrics. The addition of remote sensing Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 observations did not change the performance. Gradient boosting is recommended for forecasting with the vine age being a variable and planting density (vines ha⁻¹), row orientation and cultivar name being static predictors. Care should be taken when forecasting for fields with a low number of training data points. The models are not meant for usage outside the training areas.

Machine learning (ML) techniques were successfully used to predict and forecast agricultural crop yield (Elavarasan et al., 2018) and grape yield (Sirsat et al., 2019). eLEAF was tasked to develop a machine-learning algorithm for grape yield forecasting.

Consortium members Mastroberardino (MB), Symington (SYM) and Torres (TO) kindly provided historical yield data for ML training together with shape files and additional descriptors: cultivar name, age of vine, planting density (vines ha⁻¹) and row orientation (azimuth) degree (Table X).

Table X: The number of data points. * - the number of points that remained after the interquartile range filtering per year and per cultivar.

Producer	N plots	N points*	N years	N cultivars
Mastroberardino (MB)	22	93	6	4
Symington (SYM) Ataide	71	244	5	13
Symington (SYM) Bomfim	88	317	5	8
Torres	10	36	6	7

Additional data included weather input from the ERA5 land dataset and remote sensing data from Sentinel-1 GRD (backscatter coefficient) and Sentinel-2 level-2 (normalized difference vegetation index, NDVI). Mean, median, minimum, and maximum values of the backscatter coefficient and NDVI per plot were taken, smoothed with a 60-day moving average and summed along the growing season. ERA5 values of incoming shortwave radiation, air temperature and vapor pressure deficit were aggregated along the growing season without smoothing. The growing season was considered to start and end in September, an approximate harvest month). In this respect, the growing year was shifted 4 months backward, compared to the calendar year.

Methodology

A RandomForestRegressor from Python (version 3.10.5; sklearn package v.1.1.1, Pedregosa et al., 2011) was trained with 1000 decision trees. The results were cross validated with the StratifiedKFold with 4-10 folds. Different stratifications strategies were tried: per growing year, per producer and per cultivar. The performance was assessed by determining R^2 , MAE, RMSE and bias. The results are expressed in $q\ ha^{-1}$ (100kg per hectare).

Results

The model trained on all data together (690 points) showed the following metrics at 10-fold cross-validation stratified per producer: $R^2= 0.58 (+/-0.08)$, MAE = 9.46 (+/-0.08) $q\ ha^{-1}$, RMSE = 12.30 (+/-1.14) $q\ ha^{-1}$, bias = -0.08 (+/-1.49) $q\ ha^{-1}$ (numbers in brackets represent the standard deviation between different folds). This model had four predictors: cultivar name, age of vine, planting density (plants per ha) and row orientation (azimuth). The addition of weather data slightly improved the performance, leading to $R^2= 0.60 (+/-0.10)$ MAE = 9.03 (+/-0.10) $q\ ha^{-1}$ RMSE = 12.08 (+/-1.25) $q\ ha^{-1}$ bias = -0.31 (+/-1.44) $q\ ha^{-1}$. Remote sensing indicators from Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 did not improve the predictive power of the model significantly.

Forecasting

The aim of this work was to develop a forecasting algorithm that is able to predict values for future harvests. Among the four variables, the vine age is the one that provides such an opportunity. If weather data are included in the forecast, gradient boosting is recommended, as it showed the higher importance of meteorological variables. The aim of predicting harvest dates has been taken out of the project based on relevance and realistic detail.

The applicability of the algorithm is limited to the varieties and fields where it was trained. This limitation applies to all statistical models. In addition, care should be taken when the predictions are to be done for sites with limited availability of training samples per cultivar.

3.3 Crop Water Demand

A Crop Water Demand (CWD) Forecast model has been created and is operational within the VitiGEOSS portal. The result is the expected evapotranspiration (CWD) for the actual crop under optimally irrigated conditions for the upcoming week. The role of this tool is to provide a forecast of the amount of water needed for the crop, taking into consideration the weather forecast for the next 7 days.

The Crop Water Demand can be found among the other crop data components in the portal with a value per week in mm/week.

MONTE V 3 - grape (AGLIANICO)

● Biomass production (kg/ha): 788	● Crop water demand (mm/week): 6.33
● Crop water demand (mm/week): 10.34	● Evapotranspiration (mm/week): 6.21
● Leaf Area Index (-): 4.02	● NDVI: 0.71
● Nitrogen in canopy (kg/ha): 32.33	● Nitrogen in upper leaf layer (kg/ha): 16.55
● Potential evapotranspiration (mm/week): 6.45	● Yield Forecast: 24.65
● Yield Forecast: 24.65	

The color is based on a comparison of the value to a benchmark (+/- 15%). The benchmark is the average value of all fields in the group with the same variety.

Field properties | **Data components** | Phenology | Disease management | Sustainability

The model uses GEOS-5 weather data for the current week evapotranspiration estimates, and weather forecast (MONARCH), retrieved from BSC API, this forecasts for the next 3-days reference evapotranspiration. The result of the calculations made (see deliverable 2.2) is the expected evapotranspiration (CWD) for the actual crop under optimally irrigated conditions for the upcoming week. The Crop Water Demand forecast is provided for 7 days ahead. The Crop water demand forecast is provided in cubic meters per management unit, based on the raster information the average management unit value will be calculated.

For the implementation of this model, the short-term forecast is used to create maps for the coming three days, which will be used as input of the forecast. Additionally, the resolutions of the data have been adjusted as the short-term forecast is based on one kilometre resolution and the resolution used for the potential and reference evapotranspiration is 10 meters.

The crop water demand data is checked for anomalies before uploading, the focus is on the trendline of the data compared to previous weeks. When data spikes occur the weather forecast is the first place to look for events.

4. Disease forecast and management services

The purpose of this service is to provide the winegrower with the most reliable predictions possible about the appearance of different phytopathogens in the plots and recommendations for the application of phytosanitary products at certain doses over three different time horizons. This was done by developing statistical and Artificial Intelligence models, which have been extensively described and discussed in previous deliverables D2.2 and D2.3.

This section will show the results of the validation of short-term, sub-seasonal and seasonal disease forecast and treatment recommendation models for downy mildew (DM) and powdery mildew (PM) trained with data collected by the end-users in 2021 and tested also with real data collected in 2022. In this deliverable, the precision of the models has been detailed with a new metric (F1-Score), which is more suitable for unbalanced datasets and takes into account the combined performance of accuracy and completeness among several solutions. All models (Logistic Regression - LR; Decision Trees - DT; Random Forest - RF; Gradient Boosting - GB; K-Nearest Neighbours - KNN; Naive Bayes - NB; Support Vector Machines - SVM and Deep Neural Network - DNN) have been trained with the data from the first vegetative season (2021) and then validated with the data collected in 2022.

At this point it is necessary to mention that some data corresponding to vineyards that suffered large crop losses due to the heat waves and drought that occurred in 2022 have been removed from the validation set, as these climatic behaviours caused the leaves to wilt and consequently no symptoms of infection were recorded. It is expected, however, that they will be included for training and validation of incidence results from 2023 onwards.

4.1 Short-term models

On one hand, as could be seen in deliverable D2.2, the NB model showed a lower predictive capacity for disease risk with respect to the other models trained only with the 2021 data. This fact has not changed despite studying its precision using another metric (Table 10).

On the other hand, the average score achieved in the short-term models trained with the 2021 data is 0.945 ± 0.033 , while the score of the validation set is 0.879 ± 0.038 (-7% in average precision). Such small differences between the scores of the two datasets may suggest that the validation set is very similar to the training set and that they both reflect very little sampling variability.

Table 10. F1-Score of short-term disease and treatment prediction models trained and tested with data from the first campaign (2021) and trained with data from the first campaign and validated with data from the second campaign (2022).

Model	DM		DM		PM		PM	
	Disease Risk		Treatment		Disease Risk		Treatment	
	2021	2022	2021	2022	2021	2022	2021	2022
LR	0.977	0.879	0.945	0.826	0.945	0.925	0.892	0.858
DT	0.986	0.890	0.945	0.885	0.949	0.925	0.958	0.917
RF	0.981	0.879	0.947	0.885	0.958	0.920	0.958	0.894
GB	0.990	0.879	0.912	0.890	0.977	0.917	0.964	0.904
KNN	0.968	0.879	0.942	0.849	0.949	0.917	0.906	0.899
NB	0.904	0.879	0.945	0.789	0.835	0.859	0.936	0.776
SVM	0.972	0.876	0.945	0.885	0.977	0.923	0.892	0.917
DNN	0.977	0.837	0.945	0.817	0.926	0.898	0.945	0.863

4.2 Sub-seasonal models

The metrics of the sub-seasonal models were not yet shown in deliverable D2.2, but they are now available in column 2021 of Table 11. In this case, the average score achieved for the sub-seasonal models trained with the 2021 data is 0.933 ± 0.030 , while the score for the validation set is 0.841 ± 0.072 (-10% in average precision). Once again, slight differences between the training and the validation sets might indicate that the information present in this second dataset is very similar to the one used for model calibration, and it would be convenient to incorporate more data in 2023 to increase the variance and representativeness of the model.

Table 11. F1-Score of sub-seasonal disease and treatment prediction models trained and tested with data from the first campaign (2021) and trained with data from the first campaign and validated with data from the second campaign (2022).

Model	DM		DM		PM		PM	
	Disease Risk		Treatment		Disease Risk		Treatment	
	2021	2022	2021	2022	2021	2022	2021	2022
LR	0.968	0.884	0.942	0.750	0.903	0.937	0.961	0.781
DT	0.968	0.884	0.942	0.718	0.942	0.906	0.961	0.843
RF	0.968	0.903	0.903	0.875	0.903	0.906	0.923	0.812
GB	0.968	0.846	0.923	0.812	0.903	0.937	0.961	0.812
KNN	0.968	0.884	0.903	0.781	0.903	0.906	0.942	0.875
NB	0.906	0.884	0.942	0.812	0.846	0.843	0.942	0.843
SVM	0.968	0.884	0.942	0.750	0.903	0.906	0.942	0.875
DNN	0.906	0.826	0.942	0.718	0.903	0.906	0.961	0.625

4.3 Seasonal models

Finally, regarding the seasonal models, the average score achieved with the 2021 data was 0.913 ± 0.060 , while the validation score dropped to 0.678 ± 0.190 (-26% in average precision) (Table 12). This decrease in precision may be due to the low amount of data available for training and validation, as these are aggregated as monthly averages/accumulates and may generate disparities.

Table 12. F1-Score of seasonal disease and treatment prediction models trained and tested with data from the first campaign (2021) and trained with data from the first campaign and validated with data from the second campaign (2022).

Model	DM		DM		PM		PM	
	Disease Risk		Treatment		Disease Risk		Treatment	
	2021	2022	2021	2022	2021	2022	2021	2022
LR	0.916	0.75	0.916	0.500	0.875	0.833	1.000	0.750
DT	0.833	0.875	1.000	0.750	1.000	0.833	0.916	0.375
RF	0.916	1.000	0.833	0.375	0.750	0.833	0.916	0.375
GB	0.833	0.875	0.916	0.500	0.875	0.750	0.916	0.625
KNN	0.916	0.750	1.000	0.500	1.000	0.833	1.000	0.750
NB	0.916	0.750	0.916	0.375	0.875	0.833	0.916	0.750
SVM	0.916	0.750	0.916	0.500	0.875	0.833	0.916	0.750
DNN	0.929	0.750	0.833	0.500	0.875	0.833	1.000	0.250

Apparently, all the results observed so far seem to confirm that model overfitting was occurring with only the 2021 data that did not capture enough heterogeneity of scenarios to produce adequate predictions on its own. Models trained with 2021-2022 data and validated with 2023 are expected to further reduce this score and forecast a more realistic scenario given the data available.

5. Business and sustainability management

5.1 Sustainability indicators

In this section, a data comparison between 2021 and 2022 is presented to showcase the changes in the sustainability indicators from the first year of the application of the VitiGEOSS Intelligent Services (Table 13).

Table 13. Average value increase of the sustainability indicators from 2021 to 2022.

KPI Name	Description	2021 - 2022 value increase in %
Productivity KPI	water usage per kg yielded	-0,01 ↓
	fertilizer usage per kg yielded	-0,10 ↓
	Human labor per kg yielded	0,05 ↑
	Pesticide usage per kg yielded	-0,07 ↓
Total Water usage	Total irrigated water	-
	Disease treatment water	0,13 ↑
Water efficiency	Water usage per kg of product	-
Yield	Real yielded product	0,11 ↑
Pesticide usage	Total pesticides used	-0,03 ↓
Farm labor usage	Human labor recorded hours	0,09 ↑
Availability of farm labor	Working hours available per week	0,08 ↑

The value increases have been calculated for each individual parcel and then averaged to show a general view of the changes. It is important to note that the use of the VitiGEOSS platform is not the only factor in determining the outcome of the harvest of a land plot: other features such as meteorology or disease appearances may have a greater impact on it. Furthermore, these data have not been collected from the totality of the plots but come from the plots of most interest to the end-users, so these results should be taken with caution.

As can be seen from the results, the end users have seen an increment in the yield of their parcels to about an 11%, which is probably due to an increment of fertilizers and pesticides used. This correlates with that observed in the Productivity KPI, where a decrease means that more products have been used for each kg of fruit. Even though the availability and amount of labor usage have increased by about an 8% to 9%, the productivity regarding human labor has decreased, which means that less time has been spent for each yielded kilogram. Overall, the results show that a greater amount of yield has been achieved at the expense of fertilizers and pesticides.

During the 2023 campaign the VitiGEASS services will be fully available for the end users and the data from it will showcase their impact on the sustainability indicators much better.

5.2 Resources and tasks optimization

The task planification optimizer was tested using three real datasets from different end users. Each dataset represents a different scenario: shoot positioning on parcels using a combination of mechanized and manual workforces, soil cleaning tasks in hilly vineyards using tractors with different capacities, and consumption and harvesting management. In the following section we present a detailed description of each use-case together with the solution of the optimizer and the evaluation of the results.

5.2.1 Shoot positioning planning

The first scenario contains a set of shoot positioning tasks, together with a set of workforces with different capacities. The input dataset consists of 20 of such tasks to be organized over a period of 30 days. Each task represents performing shoot positioning on a particular parcel, and they have different work extensions depending on the size of the parcel. The tasks must be assigned to a set of 7 work teams, which have different throughputs and daily economic and environmental costs.

To illustrate the versatility of the model, we generated three different schedules by minimizing three different variables: total time spent, total economic cost and total environmental cost (Figure 30). This is equivalent to setting the priority of all the tasks to the time, economic and environmental costs respectively.

Figure 30. Three different scheduling examples of the 20 tasks. The days where a task will be performed is indicated by a coloured line, with the first and last day highlighted. The colour of the line indicates which work team has been assigned to each task.

We can observe how the algorithm spreads the tasks over all the work teams when the objective is to minimize the time spent doing the tasks (Figure 30 left). Instead, the work teams A, B and E are not employed when the objective is to minimize the economic cost, as they are the least economically efficient work teams. When the objective is to minimize the environmental impact, work teams E and F are not used, as they represent mechanized (CO2 emitting) groups.

The overall impact of having different schedules is shown in Figure 31, where the total time spent, and the overall economic and environmental costs are compared. When compared to the case where the economic cost is a priority, we observe a reduction of the time needed to finish the tasks of up 43% (from 39 to 23 days) if the manager-defined priority is the time, which in turn leads to an increase of the overall economic cost of about 13%. On the other hand, when

the priority is set to minimize the environmental cost of the tasks, results lead to an increase of 50% both in time and money to accomplish all the tasks.

Figure 31. Costs associated with the three schedules generated by prioritizing time (blue), economic cost (orange) or environmental impact (green). Each figure represents a different total cost: time to finish all the works, total economic cost, environmental cost.

5.2.2 Soil cleaning planning

The second scenario contains a set of soil cleaning tasks of four types (cutting the vines, shredding the results, spreading herbicide, and fertilizing the soil) to be performed on vineyards of four different areas during a spring campaign, which have to be assigned to a set of 4 trucks with different capacities. In this case, not all trucks are able to work on all the areas, and each type of task has a different priority. The cutting, herbicide spreading, and fertilization have to be done as soon as possible, while the shredding is not urgent and therefore should be done minimizing its economic cost. Moreover, for each type of task the window of time when it can be performed starts at different days.

Figure 32. This figure shows the planification of the task execution as designed by the optimizer.

Combining all these conditions to organize an efficient planification manually can be very cumbersome, and it is unlikely that the obtained solution would optimally use the resources. Thanks to the task planification optimizer of the VitiGEOSS Business service, a few seconds are

enough to generate the results presented in Figure 32, which shows how the tasks are organized over the campaign in order to satisfy all the constraints.

5.2.3 Harvest management

The third scenario is composed of a set of 41 tasks, each one representing a parcel of a different size that must be harvested. There is a particular work team for each task, with a specific amount of KG that it harvests per day. The limiting factor in this problem is the daily maximum amount of harvested grapes that the collection point can intake for each type of task. In this case, we have two types of harvested grapes, those collected manually (Man.) and those collected using mechanized workforces (Mech.). Therefore, the challenge is to organize the harvesting of each parcel as fast as possible, without surpassing the daily limit established for each type of grape. Additionally, the priority to harvest each parcel depends on the level of sugar in the grapes. The model accounts for this factor by using the amount of sugar in the grapes as Priority Scaler, a variable that multiplies the priority that the model gives to each task.

Figure 33 Harvest scheduling of each parcel (top) and KG harvested per day (bottom).

The planification resulting from the optimizer for this task can be observed in Figure 33. The harvesting of the parcels is organized so that it is done as fast as possible, ensuring that the parcels with high sugar levels are collected first. On the bottom, the figure also shows the amount of KG harvested per day. It can be observed how the rate of harvesting stays close to the maximum available per day until most of the parcels have been harvested and it drops.

6. Conclusion

The VitiGEOSS project is aimed at providing winemakers with a comprehensive range of services that will significantly improve vineyard management. Through the use of innovative technology systems like satellite imagery, in-field sensors, and aerial images, the project aims to provide intelligent services to facilitate access to vital information on vineyard management aspects.

This deliverable presents an overview of the performance of VitiGEOSS services: the weather and climate forecasting service, the monitoring and prediction of plant phenological cycles, the business and sustainability tool, the disease management, and the key crop indicators tracking services. The evaluation of this system was done in the second vegetative season (year 2022) through pilot plots located in Portugal, Spain, and Italy, and showed promising results. Overall they overcome the traditional methods and helped winemakers make well-informed decisions. A second evaluation will be reported in D4.7 over the third vegetative season (2023) to confirm the result presented in the present document.

Overall, the VitiGEOSS decision support system offers effective tools for enhancing the vineyard management process and has a significant impact on the development of cultivars in vineyards.

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8. ANNEXES

8.1 Deep drone analysis results

In the following pages, the results of the deep drone analysis (section 2.3) are reported, for each vineyard and each flight date.

Figure 34 - Mastroberardino, MONTE ST 1 (top) and MONTE ST 2 (bottom), 13-06-2022

Figure 35 Sentinel-2 Mastroberardino, MONTE ST 1 (top) and MONTE ST 2 (bottom), 16-06-2022

Figure 36 - Mastroberardino, MONTE ST 1 (top) and MONTE ST 2 (bottom), 28-06-2022

Figure 37 Sentinel-2 - Mastroberardino, MONTE ST 1 (top) and MONTE ST 2 (bottom), 26-06-2022

Figure 38 - Mastroberardino, MONTE ST 1 (top) and MONTE ST 2 (bottom), 29-07-2022

Figure 39 Sentinel-2 Mastroberardino, MONTE ST 1 (top) and MONTE ST 2 (bottom), 26-07-2022

Figure 40 - Mastroberardino, MONTE ST 1 (top) and MONTE ST 2 (bottom), 14-09-2022

Figure 41 Sentinel-2 Mastroberardino, MONTE ST 1 (top) and MONTE ST 2 (bottom), 14-09-2022

Figure 42 - Mastroberardino, MONTE ST 1 (top) and MONTE ST 2 (bottom), 28-10-2022

Figure 43 Sentinel-2 Mastroberardino, MONTE ST 1 (top) and MONTE ST 2 (bottom), 29-10-2022

Figure 44 - Mastroberardino, MONTE ST 3, 13-06-2022

Figure 45 Sentinel-2 Mastroberardino, MONTE ST 3, 16-06-2022

Figure 46 - Mastroberardino, MONTE ST 3, 28-06-2022

Figure 47 Sentinel-2 Mastroberardino, MONTE ST 3, 26-06-2022

Figure 48 - Mastroberardino, MONTE ST 3, 29-07-2022

Figure 49 Sentinel-2 Mastroberardino, MONTE ST 3, 26-07-2022

Figure 50 - Mastroberardino, MONTE ST 3, 14-09-2022

Figure 51 Sentinel-2 Mastroberardino, MONTE ST 3, 19-09-2022

Figure 52 - Mastroberardino, MONTE ST 3, 28-10-2022

Figure 53 Sentinel-2 Mastroberardino, MONTE ST 3, 29-10-2022

Figure 54 - Symington, ATD 94, 10-07-2022

Figure 55 Sentinel-2 Symington, ATD 94, 08-07-2022

Figure 56 - Symington, ATD 94, 24-07-2022

Figure 57 Sentinel-2 Symington, ATD 94, 23-07-2022

Figure 58 - Symington, ATD 94, 03-08-2022

Figure 59 Sentinel-2 Symington, ATD 94, 02-08-2022

Figure 60 - Symington, ATD 94, 15-08-2022

Figure 61 Sentinel-2 Symington, ATD 94, 17-08-2022

Figure 62 - Symington, ATD 94, 29-08-2022

Figure 63 Sentinel-2 Symington, ATD 94, 27-08-2022

Figure 64 - Symington, ATD 94, 10-09-2022

Figure 65 Sentinel-2 Symington, ATD 94, 16-09-2022

Figure 66 - Symington, ATD 102, 10-07-2022

Figure 67 Sentinel-2 Symington, ATD 102, 08-07-2022

Figure 68 - Symington, ATD 102, 24-07-2022

Figure 69 Sentinel-2 Symington, ATD 102, 23-07-2022

Figure 70 - Symington, ATD 102, 03-08-2022

Figure 71 Sentinel-2 Symington, ATD 102, 02-08-2022

Figure 72 - Symlington, ATD 102, 15-08-2022

Figure 73 Sentinel-2 Symlington, ATD 102, 17-08-2022

Figure 74 - Symington, ATD 102, 29-08-2022

Figure 75 Sentinel-2 Symington, ATD 102, 27-08-2022

Figure 76 - Symington, ATD 102, 10-09-2022

Figure 77 Sentinel-2 Symington, ATD 102, 16-09-2022

Figure 78 - Torres, Agrolab PM1 (top), Agrolab PM2 (center), Agrolab PM3 (bottom), 20-05-2022

Figure 79 Sentinel-2 Torres, Agrolab PM1 (top), Agrolab PM2 (center), Agrolab PM3 (bottom), 15-05-2022

Figure 80 - Torres, Agrolab PM1 (top), Agrolab PM2 (center), Agrolab PM3 (bottom), 10-06-2022

Figure 81 Sentinel-2 Torres, Agrolab PM1 (top), Agrolab PM2 (center), Agrolab PM3 (bottom), 09-06-2022

Figure 82 - Torres, Agrolab PM1 (top), Agrolab PM2 (center), Agrolab PM3 (bottom), 01-07-2022

Figure 83 Sentinel-2 Torres, Agrolab PM1 (top), Agrolab PM2 (center), Agrolab PM3 (bottom), 04-07-2022

Figure 84 - Torres, Agrolab PM1 (top), Agrolab PM2 (center), Agrolab PM3 (bottom), 29-07-2022

Figure 85 Sentinel-2 Torres, Agrolab PM1 (top), Agrolab PM2 (center), Agrolab PM3 (bottom), 24-07-2022

Figure 86 - Torres, Agrolab PM1 (top), Agrolab PM2 (center), Agrolab PM3 (bottom), 18-08-2022

Figure 87 Sentinel-2 Torres, Agrolab PM1 (top), Agrolab PM2 (center), Agrolab PM3 (bottom), 18-08-2022

Figure 88 - Torres, Agrolab PM1 (top), Agrolab PM2 (center), Agrolab PM3 (bottom), 31-08-2022

Figure 89 Sentinel-2 Torres, Agrolab PM1 (top), Agrolab PM2 (center), Agrolab PM3 (bottom), 28-08-2022

